

PGD-MAT

OBJECTIVES

This questionnaire aims to identify the maturity level of your unit in implementing the *Programa de Gestão e Desempenho (PGD)*, considering five key dimensions:

1) Planning

The organization's ability to structure delivery and work plans with clear goals aligned with the institutional strategy;

2) Task Execution

Organization and management of daily activities, including employee autonomy and team adaptability;

3) Performance Evaluation

Processes for monitoring, analyzing, and providing feedback on individual and collective performance;

4) Training, Engagement, and Culture

Level of knowledge, commitment, well-being, sense of purpose, and social connections in the work environment;

5) Tools and Data

Use of technologies, records, and data to support performance management and decision-making.

HOW TO USE

This model allows for two complementary diagnostic methods (views).

The scoring for all attributes in both views follows the same rule:

- 0: No (The practice does not exist or is not applied)
- 0.5: Sometimes (The practice exists partially, occasionally, or in a non-standardized way)
- 1: Yes (The practice exists, is applied fully and consistently)

To perform the diagnosis, follow the instructions in the Implementation Guide.

It will guide you to fill in the correct tab(s) to generate the results.

UNDERSTANDING THE RESULTS: THE TWO PERSPECTIVES

The PGD-MAT generates two types of results, both based on the assigned scores:

View 1: Maturity Level (Stages)

- **What it is:** A general diagnosis that classifies the entire organization into a single level (from 1 to 5).
- **How it is calculated:** The organization can only be classified at a given maturity level if all five of its dimensions reach an average equal to or greater than 0.75 (75%) at that level and at all previous levels.
- **Where it is used:** Useful for benchmarking and high-level communication.

View 2: Capability Level (Continuous)

- **What it is:** A detailed diagnosis that shows the organization's maturity profile, assigning a fractional level to each of the 5 dimensions (e.g., Planning 3.8, Evaluation 2.1).
- **How it's calculated:** The calculation is inspired by the continuous representation of CMMI and follows the logic of the "ladder":
 1. The Baseline Level is the last level where the dimension achieved 75% or more fulfillment.
 2. Progress is the percentage of fulfillment of the level immediately following the Baseline Level.
 3. Final Capability Level = Baseline Level + Progress (e.g., Baseline Level 2 + 67% progress at Level 3 = Capability Level 2.67).
- **Where it's used:** This is the main view for improvement planning, as it allows focusing efforts on "broken rungs" and weakest dimensions, generating a prioritized improvement roadmap.

THE DIMENSIONS AND JOURNEY OF MATURITY

Planning

Level 1: Non-existent planning or planning carried out in a way for this purpose. Work is distributed as demand arises, without predictability or alignment with broader objectives.

Level 2: It begins with basic formalization: having a unit "Delivery Plan" and individual "Work Plans." This is the minimum organizational stage.

Level 3: The capability evolves towards the use of a structured method (OKR) and collaboration, with teams participating in defining goals and breaking them down to the individual level.

Level 4: It achieves quantitative maturity by using historical data to estimate goals and deliverables and by introducing risk management.

Level 5: It reaches the strategic and adaptive level, with iterative planning, full traceability to the organization's strategy, and empowering teams to define their own goals.

Task Execution Dimension

Level 1: The execution is reactive and disorganized. Tasks are distributed and executed without a defined process, often based on emergency demands, and with little visibility into the team's work. The focus is on "putting out fires."

Level 2: It focuses on assigning and monitoring basic tasks and on the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for routine work.

Level 3: It introduces workflow management through backlogs, defined cycles, and follow-up rituals (e.g., daily meetings).

Level 4: Formalize the cycles with the concept of sprints, and, crucially, it introduces the cycle of feedback and improvement through review and retrospective meetings.

Level 5: It achieves autonomy and optimization, with teams performing self-diagnostics, adjusting their own processes, and organizing themselves into cross-functional teams (squads).

Performance Evaluation Dimension

Level 1: Non-existent or entirely informal. There is no structured evaluation process. Feedback, when it occurs, is sporadic, subjective, and reactive to isolated events, with no connection to goals or career development.

Level 2: A monitoring ritual is established, with goal review, end-of-cycle evaluation, and periodic feedback.

Level 3: The process becomes more formal and qualified, with clearer criteria, recording of results, and more structured feedback sessions.

Level 4: It evolves into a quantitative assessment, with the use of benchmarks and SLAs.

Level 5: It reaches its peak with 360° evaluation and a focus on collective learning.

Training, Engagement, and Culture

Level 1: The environment is reactive and purely transactional. There are no planned actions for training, engagement, or cultural development. The culture is focused on the immediate task, with a low sense of collective purpose and little psychological safety.

Level 2: Initial training and specific integration and recognition initiatives.

Level 3: It evolves into structured processes: identifying skills gaps, periodic training, and formal listening spaces.

Level 4: It becomes data-driven, with climate and engagement assessments generating institutional improvement plans.

Level 5: It reaches a human-centered level, focusing on well-being, empowerment, a culture of recognition, and active monitoring of the mental health of employees.

Tools and Data Dimension

Level 1: The use of basic and non-standardized tools. Management is based on individual controls. There is no centralized data source, which makes it impossible to generate performance indicators and make evidence-based decisions.

Level 2: The capability is for recording and control. The tools serve to know the basics: what, who, when, and what the status is.

Level 3: It evolves towards data and context generation. The tools begin to classify by complexity and consolidate historical data, generating the first indicators.

Level 4: It achieves predictive capability. The tools begin to use historical data to support future decision-making.

Level 5: The tools support strategic management, with full data integration, Business Intelligence, and dashboards in real time to support decisions at all levels.

REFERENCES

The PGD-MAT is a research artifact built upon established models and adapted to the reality of the *Programa de Gestão e Desempenho (PGD)*. The main sources that inspire the attributes and maturity progression are:

- **PGD Guide:** The official guidelines of the federal government for structuring Delivery Plans and Work Plans.

- **CMMI (Capability Maturity Model Integration):** Provides the maturity framework by levels and key process areas such as Monitoring and Control, Risk Management, and Quantitative Management.

- **MPS-RH (MPS Reference Model for People Management):** Brazilian model that underpins the practices of Training, Performance Evaluation, and Climate and Engagement Management.

- **Agile Methodologies (Scrum/Kanban):** Inspire the practices of execution in short cycles, rituals (dailies, retrospectives), backlogs, and multifunctional teams.

- **OKR (Objectives and Key Results):** Provides the foundation for collaborative goal setting practices, strategic alignment, and connection to purpose.

- **DX-CMM (Digital Transformation Capability Maturity Model):** Inspires the evolution of the Tools and Data dimension as a pillar of digital transformation.

- **Industry 5.0:** Provides the concepts of Human-Centeredness and Sustainability (focus on well-being and burnout prevention) that characterize the highest level of maturity.

	1. INITIAL	2. MANAGED	3. DEVELOPED	4. QUANTITATIVELY MANAGED	5. EXCELLENCE								
PLANNING Level 1: Planning is nonexistent or carried out ad hoc. Work is distributed as demand arises, without predictability or alignment with larger objectives. Level 2: Begins with basic formalization: having a unit "Deliverables Plan" and individual "Work Plans." This is the stage of minimal organization. Level 3: Capability evolves to the use of a structured method (OKR) and collaboration, with teams participating in goal setting and breaking them down to the individual level. Level 4: Reaches quantitative maturity, using historical data to estimate goals and deliverables and introducing risk management. Level 5: Reaches the strategic and adaptive level, with iterative planning, full traceability to the organization's strategy, and empowerment of teams in defining their own goals.	EXPECTED RESULT [PLA1.1] Planning occurs without predictability. [PLA1.2] Activities performed without defined goals, scope, or deadlines. [PLA1.3] Lack of shared objectives among team members.	EXPECTED RESULT [PLA2.1] The unit has a delivery plan for the current year. [PLA2.2] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined target. [PLA2.3] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined deadline. [PLA2.4] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined requester. [PLA2.5] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined recipient. [PLA2.6] The unit's delivery plan is reviewed at defined intervals. [PLA2.7] Each member of the PGD has an individual work plan. [PLA2.8] Individual work plans indicate their period of validity. [PLA2.9] Individual work plans indicate the distribution of the owner's working hours during the period of validity. [PLA2.10] The criteria that will be used by the supervisor to evaluate the individual work plan are defined in the individual work plans. [PLA2.11] Individual work plans are derived from, or explicitly aligned with, the deliverables defined in the unit plan.	REFERENCE PGD Guide (Structure of the Delivery Plan and Work Plan)	EXPECTED RESULT [PLA3.1] The organization uses OKR, defining measurable operational goals. [PLA3.2] Team members contribute to defining cycle goals. [PLA3.3] The progress toward the defined goals is frequently reviewed and updated. [PLA3.4] Organizational goals are reviewed and redefined periodically. [PLA3.5] The organization breaks down its operational goals into team deliverables. [PLA3.6] Team deliverables are broken down into individual plan deliverables for their members, allowing for traceability of the origin.	REFERENCE OKR (Principles: Goal Setting, Alignment, and Cycles) OKR (Principles: Goal Setting, Alignment, and Cycles) CMMI (Process Area: Requirements Management - REQM)	EXPECTED RESULT [PLA4.1] Operational goals are estimated based on historical data. [PLA4.2] Team deliverables are estimated based on historical data. [PLA4.3] Individual deliveries are estimated based on historical data. [PLA4.4] Risks and dependencies related to operational goals are identified and monitored. [PLA4.5] The risks and dependencies related to team deliverables are identified and monitored. [PLA4.6] Mitigation plans exist for targets with identified risks. [PLA4.7] Mitigation plans exist for deliveries with identified risks.	REFERENCE CMMI (Process Area: Quantitative Project Management - QPM) CMMI (Process Area: Risk Management - RSKM)	EXPECTED RESULT [PLA5.1] Planning is carried out iteratively, with adjustments based on performance data. [PLA5.2] There is traceability between operational goals and the actions of the organization's tactical and strategic plans. [PLA5.3] The definition of strategic goals is carried out with the participation of stakeholders. [PLA5.4] As foreseen in the OKR, some of the operational goals are defined by the team itself.	REFERENCE Agile Methodologies (Principle: Responding to Change and Continuous Improvement) CMMI (Process Area: Organizational Performance Management - OPM) OKR (Principles: Autonomy and Strategic Alignment)				
	TASK EXECUTION Level 1: Execution is reactive and disorganized. Tasks are distributed and executed without a defined process, often based on emergency demands and with little visibility of the team's work. The focus is on "putting out fires." Level 2: Focuses on the assignment and basic monitoring of tasks and the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for routine work. Level 3: Introduces workflow management through backlogs, defined cycles, and monitoring rituals (daily meetings). Level 4: Formalizes cycles with the concept of sprints and, crucially, introduces the feedback and improvement cycle with review and retrospective meetings. Level 5: Achieves autonomy and optimization, with teams performing self-diagnostics, adjusting their own processes, and organizing themselves into cross-functional teams (squads).	EXPECTED RESULT [EXE1.1] Tasks are executed on demand, without planning. [EXE1.2] Tasks executed without formal logging or logs stored without standardization. [EXE1.3] PGD members work in isolation. [EXE1.4] There is little or no integration between teams for delivering results. [EXE1.5] Task assignment occurs informally, without systematic recording or traceability.	EXPECTED RESULT [EXE2.1] Deliverables are assigned to PGD participants in a planned manner. [EXE2.2] It is possible to track the delivery status of all PGD participants. [EXE2.3] The status of deliveries is recorded and reflects the actual progress of their execution. [EXE2.4] When a delivery is completed, its completion date is recorded. [EXE2.5] When a delivery is completed, its complexity is recorded. [EXE2.6] PGD member deliverables are categorized in a predictable classification.	REFERENCE CMMI (Process Area: Project Monitoring and Control - PMC)	EXPECTED RESULT [EXE3.1] Teams have a structured list of tasks (backlog) to be executed in a cycle. [EXE3.2] The duration of task execution cycles is well defined. [EXE3.3] Teams review and prioritize their backlogs periodically. [EXE3.4] The teams conduct daily meetings to oversee activities and address obstacles. [EXE3.5] Activities are performed following defined processes. [EXE3.6] For routine and repetitive activities, there are documented standard operating procedures (SOPs) accessible to the team.	REFERENCE Agile Methodologies (Scrum Framework: Rituals and Artifacts) CMMI (Process Area: Organizational Process Focus - OPF) CMMI (Process Area: Organizational Process Definition - OPD)	EXPECTED RESULT [EXE4.1] The execution of activities necessary to make deliveries is done in cycles. [EXE4.2] There is monitoring of team performance during the execution of work cycles (sprints). [EXE4.3] Work cycle (sprint) review meetings are held. [EXE4.4] Retrospective meetings are held for the work cycles (sprints). [EXE4.5] Results from retrospective meetings are documented and used for future adjustments. [EXE4.6] The team is encouraged to use performance data (time, volume, errors) to propose and test improvements to its work processes and procedures.	REFERENCE Agile Methodologies (Scrum Framework: Sprints, Sprint Reviews, Retrospectives) CMMI (Process Area: Causal Analysis and Resolution - CAR)	EXPECTED RESULT [EXE5.1] Teams perform self-assessments of operational efficiency at the end of each cycle. [EXE5.2] Adjustments to the execution of activities are made according to the results of the teams' self-diagnosis. [EXE5.3] There is an integration between teams to create cross-functional teams, in order to perform activities (squads). [EXE5.4] Execution cycles are continuously adjusted based on performance. [EXE5.5] Execution cycles are continuously adjusted based on identified risks. [EXE5.6] Execution cycles are continuously adjusted based on feedback. [EXE5.7] Teams have established Service Level Agreements (SLAs) for the provision of internal services.	REFERENCE Agile Methodologies (Principle: Self-organizing Teams and Continuous Improvement) Agile Methodologies (Principle: Self-organizing Teams and Continuous Improvement)			
		PERFORMANCE EVALUATION Level 1: Non-existent or completely informal. There is no structured evaluation process. Feedback, when it occurs, is sporadic, subjective, and reactive to isolated events, without connection to goals or career development. Level 2: A monitoring ritual is established, with goal review, end-of-cycle evaluation, and periodic feedback. Level 3: The process becomes more formal and qualified, with clearer criteria, recording of results, and more structured feedback sessions. Level 4: Evolves to quantitative evaluation, with the use of benchmarks and SLAs. Level 5: Reaches its peak with 360° evaluation and a focus on collective learning.	EXPECTED RESULT [AVA1.1] There are no well-defined criteria for performance evaluation. [AVA1.2] There are no clear performance goals for PGD members. [AVA1.3] Performance evaluation based solely on the supervisor's personal impression. [AVA1.4] Feedback is rare or offered inadequately by management.	EXPECTED RESULT [AVA2.1] There are defined outcome targets for each delivery category. [AVA2.2] There are performance goals defined for each member of the PGD. [AVA2.3] The performance evaluation criteria are well-defined and clear to all members of the PGD. [AVA2.4] Team leaders periodically review the performance goals of their team members. [AVA2.5] Performance evaluations occur at the end of each PGD cycle. [AVA2.6] Team leaders periodically provide feedback on the performance of their subordinates.	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Process: Performance Evaluation - PDE) MPS-RH (Process: Climate and Engagement Management - GCE)	EXPECTED RESULT [AVA3.1] Performance evaluations are conducted regularly and with clear criteria: delivery, effort, collaboration. [AVA3.2] There are well-defined criteria for performance evaluation. E.g., value delivered, effort, and collaboration. [AVA3.3] There is a (retrievable) record of the performance evaluation results. [AVA3.4] Based on the results of the performance evaluation, feedback sessions are conducted by the leadership. [AVA3.5] Feedback sessions include a discussion of how individual deliverables contribute to team goals, reinforcing the overall vision.	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Process: Performance Evaluation - PDE) OKR (Principle: Connection with Purpose)	EXPECTED RESULT [AVA4.1] The organization has benchmarks by type of activity, defined from historical data. [AVA4.2] Comparisons are made between employee performance and defined benchmarks. [AVA4.3] Benchmarks are continuously revised based on new data. [AVA4.4] The organization has defined service level agreements (SLAs) for services performed (e.g., user tickets). [AVA4.5] Service level agreements (SLAs) are continuously reviewed based on new data.	REFERENCE CMMI (Process Area: Measurement and Analysis - MA)	EXPECTED RESULT [AVA5.1] Performance reviews are conducted in a 360° format, where team members evaluate each other. [AVA5.2] Performance reviews are conducted in a 360° format, where leaders evaluate subordinates. [AVA5.3] Performance reviews are conducted in a 360° format, where subordinates evaluate leaders. [AVA5.4] 360° assessments drive collective learning cycles and on-demand training.	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Process: Performance Evaluation - PDE) MPS-RH (Processes: Performance Evaluation - PEE and Training - TRAINING)		
			TRAINING, ENGAGEMENT, AND CULTURE Level 1: The environment is reactive and purely transactional. There are no planned actions for training, engagement, or culture development. The culture is focused on the immediate task, with a low sense of collective purpose and little psychological safety. Level 2: Begins with the basics: initial training and specific integration and recognition actions. Level 3: Evolves into structured processes: identification of training gaps, periodic training, and formal listening spaces. Level 4: Becomes data-driven, with climate and engagement assessments generating institutional improvement plans. Level 5: Reaches a human-centric level, focusing on well-being, empowerment, a culture of recognition, and active monitoring of the mental health of employees.	EXPECTED RESULT [CEC1.1] Training opportunities are rare. [CEC1.2] There are no formal criteria or plan for training. [CEC1.3] There is no culture that promotes recognition for good results.	EXPECTED RESULT [CEC2.1] Teams are trained in an introduction to remote work and the PGD. [CEC2.2] Specific team integration activities are carried out. [CEC2.3] Leaders are trained in managing hybrid teams (in-person and remote work). [CEC2.4] Leaders reinforce desirable behaviors and promote engagement through recognition, such as public thanks or informal mentions.	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Process: Training - CAP) MPS-RH (Process: Climate and Engagement Management - GCE) MPS-RH (Process: Training - CAP)	EXPECTED RESULT [CEC3.1] There is a well-defined process for identifying skills gaps. [CEC3.2] Periodic training sessions are conducted based on identified needs. [CEC3.3] Leaders are trained in agile management and processes. [CEC3.4] There are formal spaces for listening and collective participation. [CEC3.5] Regular actions are promoted to integrate and strengthen ties between employees.	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Processes: Personnel Allocation - ALP) MPS-RH (Process: Climate and Engagement Management (GCE))	EXPECTED RESULT [CEC4.1] Periodic climate and engagement assessments are conducted. [CEC4.2] There is a use of employee listening data to define people management actions. [CEC4.3] The results of climate and engagement assessments generate public action plans for improving well-being and the work environment. [CEC4.4] Leaders are trained in conflict management. [CEC4.5] Leaders are trained on feedback (including remote work)	REFERENCE MPS-RH (Process: Climate and Engagement Management - GCE) MPS-RH (Processes: Training - CAP and Leadership Development - DEL)	EXPECTED RESULT [CEC5.1] The work environment is centered on empowerment and well-being. [CEC5.2] The organization has a culture of recognizing employee work. [CEC5.3] Leaders are trained in managing high-performance teams. [CEC5.4] Symbolic and institutional recognition is integrated into the organization's rituals (e.g., events, official announcements, public dashboards). [CEC5.5] Institutional communication continuously connects the PGD deliverables to the impact generated for society, reinforcing the sense of purpose. [CEC5.6] The organization actively monitors the workload and stress levels of employees, implementing actions to prevent burnout.	REFERENCE Industry 5.0 (Pillar: Human-centeredness / Focus on Empowerment) Industry 5.0 (Pillar: Human-centeredness / Sense of Purpose) Industry 5.0 (Pillar: Sustainability / Well-being and Mental Health)	
				TOOLS AND DATA Level 1: Use of basic and non-standardized tools. Management is based on individual controls. There is no centralized data source, making it impossible to generate performance indicators and make evidence-based decisions. Level 2: The capacity is for recording and control. The tools serve to know the basics: what, who, when, and what the status is. Level 3: Evolves to the generation of data and context. The tools begin to classify by complexity and consolidate historical data, generating the first indicators. Level 4: Reaches predictive capacity. The tools begin to use historical data to support future decision-making. Level 5: The tools support strategic management, with full data integration, Business Intelligence, and real-time dashboards to support decisions at all levels.	EXPECTED RESULT [FER1.1] There are no standardized tools for recording deliveries. [FER1.2] Delivery results are not recorded or are scattered across documents.	EXPECTED RESULT [FER2.1] Deliveries are recorded in a single software tool for the organization, with individual and identified access. [FER2.2] Deliveries recorded in the organization's standard software are categorized in a predictable classification. [FER2.3] Deliveries recorded in the organization's standard software have their responsible party identified. [FER2.4] Deliveries recorded in the organization's standard software have a status that reflects their progress. [FER2.5] Deliverables recorded in the organization's standard software have a start date and an end (completion) date. [FER2.6] In the standard software tool, it is possible to report problems or impediments during the execution of deliveries. [FER2.7] In the standard software tool, it is possible to obtain simple reports with the deliverables of a given PGD participant, within a given period.	REFERENCE PGD Guide (Data System and Transmission) DX-CMM (Dimension: Technology - Data Management and Tools)	EXPECTED RESULT [FER3.1] Deliverables are categorized by their complexity in the software tool used for recording. [FER3.2] From the delivery registration tool, it is possible to obtain consolidated historical data (indicators). [FER3.3] There is an integration between software tools that allows identifying all activities performed by employees, whether planned or not (e.g., user tickets).	REFERENCE PGD Guide (Data System and Transmission) DX-CMM (Dimension: Technology - Data Analysis)	EXPECTED RESULT [FER4.1] It is possible to view activities in dashboards, with benchmark indicators. [FER4.2] Based on historical data, the activity logging tool is able to provide predictive duration information using artificial intelligence. [FER4.3] Based on historical data, the activity logging tool is able to offer predictive information of complexity, using artificial intelligence.	REFERENCE DX-CMM (Dimension: Technology - Data Analysis) DX-CMM (Dimension: Technology - Artificial Intelligence and Analytics)	EXPECTED RESULT [FER5.1] The activities of all teams in the organization are stored in an integrated way or in a single tool, with performance history available. [FER5.2] Using data for decision making and predictive planning (Business Intelligence). [FER5.3] Dynamic dashboards with real-time data are used for operational and strategic decisions.	REFERENCE DX-CMM (Dimension: Strategy - Data-driven Decision making)

DIMENSION	AVERAGE	SITUATION	ATTRIBUTE	ASSESSMENT
PLANNING	0,75	MET	[PLA3.1] The organization uses OKR, defining measurable operational goals.	Sometimes
			[PLA3.2] Team members contribute to defining cycle goals.	Yes
			[PLA3.3] The progress toward the defined goals is frequently reviewed and updated.	Sometimes
			[PLA3.4] Organizational goals are reviewed and redefined periodically.	Yes
			[PLA3.5] The organization breaks down its operational goals into team deliverables.	Yes
			[PLA3.6] Team deliverables are broken down into individual plan deliverables for their members, allowing for traceability of the origin.	Sometimes
TASK EXECUTION	0,67	NOT MET	[EXE3.1] Teams have a structured list of tasks (backlog) to be executed in a cycle.	Sometimes
			[EXE3.2] The duration of task execution cycles is well defined.	Sometimes
			[EXE3.3] Teams review and prioritize their backlogs periodically.	Yes
			[EXE3.4] The teams conduct daily meetings to oversee activities and address obstacles	Sometimes
			[EXE3.5] Activities are performed following defined processes.	Sometimes
			[EXE3.6] For routine and repetitive activities, there are documented standard operating procedures (SOPs) accessible to the team.	Yes
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	0,40	NOT MET	[AVA3.1] Performance evaluations are conducted regularly and with clear criteria: delivery, effort, collaboration.	No
			[AVA3.2] There are well-defined criteria for performance evaluation. E.g., value delivered, effort, and collaboration.	Sometimes
			[AVA3.3] There is a (retrievable) record of the performance evaluation results.	No
			[AVA3.4] Based on the results of the performance evaluation, feedback sessions are conducted by the leadership.	Sometimes
			[AVA3.5] Feedback sessions include a discussion of how individual deliverables contribute to team goals, reinforcing the overall vision.	Yes
TRAINING, ENGAGEMENT AND CULTURE	0,90	MET	[CEC3.1] There is a well-defined process for identifying skills gaps.	Yes
			[CEC3.2] Periodic training sessions are conducted based on identified needs.	Yes
			[CEC3.3] Leaders are trained in agile management and processes.	Sometimes
			[CEC3.4] There are formal spaces for listening and collective participation.	Yes
			[CEC3.5] Regular actions are promoted to integrate and strengthen ties between employees.	Yes
TOOLS AND DATA	0,67	NOT MET	[FER3.1] Deliverables are categorized by their complexity in the software tool used for recording.	Sometimes
			[FER3.2] From the delivery registration tool, it is possible to obtain consolidated historical data (indicators).	Yes
			[FER3.3] There is an integration between software tools that allows identifying all activities performed by employees, whether planned or not (e.g., user tickets).	Sometimes

PLANNING

LEVEL	AVERAGE	SITUATION	ATTRIBUTE	ASSESSMENT
2	0,77	MET	[PLA2.1] The unit has a delivery plan for the current year.	Sometimes
			[PLA2.2] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined target.	Yes
			[PLA2.3] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined deadline.	Sometimes
			[PLA2.4] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined requester.	Sometimes
			[PLA2.5] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined recipient.	Yes
			[PLA2.6] The unit's delivery plan is reviewed at defined intervals.	Yes
			[PLA2.7] Each member of the PGD has an individual work plan.	Sometimes
			[PLA2.8] Individual work plans indicate their period of validity.	Sometimes
			[PLA2.9] Individual work plans indicate the distribution of the owner's working hours during the period of validity.	Yes
			[PLA2.10] The criteria that will be used by the supervisor to evaluate the individual work plan are defined in the individual work plans.	Yes
			[PLA2.11] Individual work plans are derived from, or explicitly aligned with, the deliverables defined in the unit plan.	Yes
3	0,67	NOT MET	[PLA3.1] The organization uses OKR, defining measurable operational goals.	Sometimes
			[PLA3.2] Team members contribute to defining cycle goals.	Sometimes
			[PLA3.3] The progress toward the defined goals is frequently reviewed and updated.	Yes
			[PLA3.4] Organizational goals are reviewed and redefined periodically.	No
			[PLA3.5] The organization breaks down its operational goals into team deliverables.	Yes
			[PLA3.6] Team deliverables are broken down into individual plan deliverables for their members, allowing for traceability of the origin.	Yes
4	0,43	NOT MET	[PLA4.1] Operational goals are estimated based on historical data.	Sometimes
			[PLA4.2] Team deliverables are estimated based on historical data.	No
			[PLA4.3] Individual deliveries are estimated based on historical data.	No
			[PLA4.4] Risks and dependencies related to operational goals are identified and monitored.	Sometimes
			[PLA4.5] The risks and dependencies related to team deliverables are identified and monitored.	Sometimes
			[PLA4.6] Mitigation plans exist for targets with identified risks.	Yes
			[PLA4.7] Mitigation plans exist for deliveries with identified risks.	Sometimes
5	0,38	NOT MET	[PLA5.1] Planning is carried out iteratively, with adjustments based on performance data.	No
			[PLA5.2] There is traceability between operational goals and the actions of the organization's tactical and strategic plans.	Sometimes
			[PLA5.3] The definition of strategic goals is carried out with the participation of stakeholders.	No
			[PLA5.4] As foreseen in the OKR, some of the operational goals are defined by the team itself.	Yes
			Highest level completed	2
			Next level progress	0,67
			Capacity Level	2,67